

Template - Processing analysis

Template to process all surfaces acquired with the LSM with the 50x/0.75 and 50x/0.95 objectives.

Processing

Identity card			
Name:	MudPlaster2015MEGII_LSM_50x_type2_e_Topo		
Created on:	4/12/2021 5:01:13 PM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	15.08	μm	
Size:	65532	digits	
Spacing:	0.2301	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	MudPlaster2015MEGII...filtered (As 2.500 μm)		
File path:	D:\Dropbox\jmmarreir...0x_type2_e_Topo.sur		
Created on:	4/12/2021 5:01:13 PM		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	0.000	μm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	-255.5	μm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	4.510	μm	
Min:	-2.611	μm	
Max:	1.900	μm	
Size:	196010	digits	
Spacing:	0.02301	nm	
NM-points ratio:	3.391 % (305231 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	MudPlaster2015MEGII_...in non-measured points		
Created on:	4/12/2021 5:01:13 PM		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	4.510	μm	
Size:	196010	digits	
Spacing:	0.02301	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Analyses

8. ISO 25178-2 parameters on surface #7

ISO 25178 - Primary surface			
<i>F: [Workflow] Form removed (LS-poly 3)</i>			
<i>S-filter (λs): [Workflow] S-filtered (λs 2.500 μm)</i>			
Height parameters			
Sq	0.5815	μm	
Ssk	-0.707		
Sku	4.475		
Sp	1.897	μm	
Sv	2.614	μm	
Sz	4.510	μm	
Sa	0.4453	μm	
Functional parameters			
Smr	3.243	%	
Smc	0.6579	μm	
Sxp	1.432	μm	
Spatial parameters			
Sal	14.87	μm	
Str	0.4351		
Std	37.75	°	
Hybrid parameters			
Sdq	0.1471		
Sdr	1.040	%	
Functional parameters (Volume)			
Vm	0.02283	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vv	0.6808	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmp	0.02283	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmc	0.4883	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvc	0.5922	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvv	0.08855	μm ³ /μm ²	

Analyses:	
ISO 25178	8.
Furrow	9.
Texture direction	10.
Texture isotropy	11.
SSFA	12.

9. Furrow analysis on surface #7

All furrows are shown.

Parameters	Value	Unit
Maximum depth of furrows	2.951	µm
Mean depth of furrows	0.6218	µm
Mean density of furrows	3523	cm/cm2

10. Texture direction on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
First direction	26.46	°
Second direction	0.001359	°
Third direction	45.01	°

11. Texture isotropy on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
Texture isotropy	41.15	%

12. SSFA on surface #7

